

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

AGROBIOLOGIC METHOD OF CONTROL OF THE FUSARIUM WILT OF COTTON IN UZBEKISTAN

**Marupov A.,
Turamuratova G.,
Marupov U.**

*Research institute of quarantine and plant protection,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

ABSTRACT

It has been established that during soil solarization, the causative agent of the wilt fungus *Fusarium* sp. is eradicated in the arable horizon, along with it, other soil microorganisms are also destroyed. Soil greening after solarization restores the natural microbiological potential of the soil and increases its antibiotic activity, as well as reduces the incidence of wilt plants at an early stage of their development, preserves the number of plants and increases the cotton yield.

Keywords: Fusarium wilt, pathogen, microorganisms, soil, solarization, mustard, cotton.

Introduction. Global climate change affects not only higher plants, but also plant pests. Ensuring food security directly depends on the protection of cultivated crops from harmful organisms that cause great damage to the crop and its quality.

In recent years, in Uzbekistan, there has been an increasing damage to zoned cotton varieties by Fusarium wilt, caused by a soil wilt pathogenic fungus from the genus *Fusarium*.

A particularly new form of Fusarium wilt pathogen caused by a fungus *Fusarium verticillioides* (Sacc.) Nirenberg causes significant damage to young cotton plants in the Bukhara and Navoi regions, as a result, the latter die and their density on the field is greatly reduced. Plants affected by wilt lose their yield, the quality of cotton fiber and the quality of seeds deteriorate.

Failure to use anti-wilt measures on farms can cause repetition of wilt epiphytoses on cotton that arose in the 60s and 70s of the last century.

President of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, at a selector meeting held on May 25, 2021, specifically pointed out "On measures to improve plant protection systems", emphasized the improvement of research work in the field of combating cotton wilt disease in the Bukhara region.

The wilt pathogen constantly accumulates in the soil, and not the use of scientifically based anti-wilt crop rotation on farms only contributes to the defeat of new cotton varieties, due to the high adaptive ability of pathogens to new zoned varieties.

The increase in wilt damage to zoned cotton varieties is facilitated by non-compliance with the phytosanitary condition of the fields, as well as the spread of highly virulent and aggressive forms (races) of pathogens that constantly accumulate in the soil during permanent cultivation of the same cotton variety.

A large number of dormant forms of the pathogen (microsclerotia or chlamydospores) are formed on infected plants or their residues, when they are embedded in the soil, as a result of the decomposition of plant residues, they fall back into the soil and cause an increase in infection.

K. Baker (Baker, 1968) found that one cotton plant infected with verticillium can leave about 250 thousand microsclerotia in the soil.

In cotton fields, the main number of *V. dahliae* is infected in the horizon up to 40 cm, and the number of fungi is low in the horizons below 40 cm (Mirpulatova, 1969; Kireeva, 1972; Ramazonova and Gulyamova, 1974; Marupov, 1993; 2003).

The adaptation of the pathogen to a high level of residence in the soil and the exactingness of plants to the agroecological environment allow pathogens to remain in the soil for a long time, which makes it difficult to fight them.

According to N.S. Mirpulatova (1973), wilt pathogens are mainly located at a depth of 5-25 cm in the arable soil layer. The favorable temperature for the vital activity of the wilting fungus is 24-26°C, at 28°C it stops developing and dies at temperatures above 30°C.

Therefore, the eradication of the causative agent of wilt in the soil is a very productive way to fight.

N. Kenneth and Y. Katan (1972); Y. Katan (1981); Y. Katan and J. De Vey (1991); A. Jamliel and Y. Katan (2012) used soil solarization against soil pathogens of cotton, vegetables and other crops as one of the radical methods of dealing with them.

With this method, when the soil was covered with a film of 0.038-0.050 mm for 7-8 weeks, the soil temperature was 42-55°C at a depth of 5-10 cm and 32-37°C at a depth of 45 cm, DeVay, 1991).

This method is widely used in the USA, Israel, Australia, Spain and other countries against soil pathogens. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, this method has not been previously used and is a new innovative approach in the fight against soil pathogens, especially in the fight against cotton wilt. In Uzbekistan, the method of soil solarization in the fight against soil pathogens has not been studied before.

Back in 1992, we planned a joint study with professors J. Katan (J. Katan, Hebrew Univ., Isr.) and J.E. De Vay (Davis Univ., CA, USA), but due to lack of funds were able to realize this idea.

Materials and methods of research

Experiments on this problem were carried out in 2015-2016 on a naturally heavily contaminated field of the farm named after. "Kulkhatib" Vobkent district of the Bukhara region.

Experience Options

1. Cotton by cotton
2. Wheat + cotton
3. Wheat + solarization + cotton
4. Wheat + solarization + mustard (green manure) + cotton

The experience was laid according to the methodology (Soyuz NIHI, 1981).

After harvesting wheat for grain, the experimental plot was prepared for sowing according to the generally accepted method in the farm (July 11). Then, according to the variants of the experiment, the plots were covered with a film of 0.05 in size (July 17). After 48 days, i.e. On September 4, the film was removed from the experimental plots. According to the variants of the experiment, mustard was sown (September 5) according to the recommendation of A. Marupov (1988).

Microbiological analyzes of the soil were carried out after harvesting wheat (July 11) and after solarization of the soil (September 29) before sowing mustard according to the generally accepted method of limiting dilutions according to S.F. Lazarev (1963).

Soil samples for analysis were taken from a horizon of 0-40 cm before sowing plants, during the budding period and during flowering - the fruiting of cotton. The growth of bacteria was determined on meat peptone agar (MPA), actinomycetes - on ammonium starch medium (ASM) and fungi - on Czapek's medium with pH 4.5-5. Czapek's medium was acidified with 50% citric acid. Accounts of isolated colonies of microorganisms were carried out on days 3-5-7.

Growing mustard was fed with nitrogen at a rate of 50 kg/ha. Plants were watered 3 times during the growing season.

When plants reached a height of 1.0 m, their Phyto mass was crushed and plowed into the soil to a depth of 40 cm (November 10). When plowing mustard Phyto mass, 70% of phosphorus and 50% of potassium were added from the annual rate of cotton fertilizer (Marupov, 1988).

In 2016, Bukhara-10 cotton was sown at the optimal time for the farmer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The data of the microbiological analysis of the soil (2015) after harvesting wheat and after solarization of the soil are given in Table 1. From the data in the table, it can be seen that after harvesting wheat (July 11), the total number of fungi is 9.0 thousand, bacteria 42.0 thousand. pcs and actinomycetes 10.0 million pcs in 1g. abs. dry soil.

Table 1.

The total number of microorganisms in 1 g abs. dry soil.
Bukhara region, Vobkent district, farm "Kulkhatib", Variety Bukhara-10
2015

№	Experience options	Fungus, thous.	Bacteria, thous.	Actenomyces, mln.
After the wheat harvest (July 11)				
	Wheat	9,0	42,0	10,0
After solarization of the soil (September 4)				
1	Cotton by cotton	10,0	76,0	9,25
2	Wheat	11,7	116,0	9,27
3	Wheat + solarization	2,0	50,5	7,15

In the same variant (September 4), an increase in the total number of microorganisms is noted due to the enrichment of the loot layer of soil with root and stubble residues of wheat. The total number of fungi is 11.7 thousand pieces, bacteria 116.0 thousand pieces and actinomycetes 9.27 million pieces in 1g abs. dry soil.

Under cotton (owner's sowing), these indicators were respectively 10.0 for microorganisms; 76.0 and 9.25 mln. in 1 g abs. dry soil.

In the variant where soil solarization was carried out, the total number of microorganisms declined

sharply and their number was: fungi 2.0 thousand pieces, bacteria 50.5 thousand pieces and actinomycetes 7.15 million pieces in 1 g abs. dry soil. Isolation of fungi of the genus *Fusarium* from the soil was not observed. Thermophilic fungi from the genus *Aspergillus* dominated mainly (Fig. 1). Despite a significant decrease in the number of bacteria from 116.0 to 50.5 thousand pieces in 1 g abs. dry soil, among them there were many colonies with antagonistic activity against the *Fusarium* fungus, which is of great theoretical and practical interest in further research (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Fungus under cotton, after wheat harvest and after solarization.

Fig. 2. Bacterial antagonists after solarization and sideration.

A decrease in the total number of actinomycetes was also observed. Its number of microorganisms declined sharply and their number was: fungi 2.0 thousand pieces, bacteria 50.5 thousand pieces and actinomycetes 7.15 million pieces in 1 g abs. dry soil. Isolation of fungi of the genus *Fusarium* from the soil was not observed.

Apparently, the high temperature and humidity of the soil created under the film inhibit the total number of microorganisms, especially fungi.

This pattern indicates the need to replenish the arable horizon of the soil with the necessary organic materials in order to restore the beneficial natural microbiological potential of the soil after solarization.

In our experiments, mustard served as such a material.

Harvest of green manure culture of mustard before ploughing. According to the variants of the experiment, after harvesting the film, we sowed mustard on September 5th. During the vegetation period, the plants were irrigated twice. Once fed with nitrogen at a rate of 30 kg/ha.

The density of standing plants before plowing was 310.0 thousand pieces. per hectare. The average height of the stems was 95.0 cm. In total, the green mass of mustard with roots was plowed under the fall - 532.0 kg / ha.

In 2016, against a prepared background, in 2015, cotton planting of the Bukhara-10 variety was sown.

Microbiological analyzes of the soil. Table 1 shows the data of microbiological analysis of the soil before sowing and during the period of cotton ripening. From the data of Table 1, it can be seen that with cotton monoculture, the total number of fungi before cotton sowing is 7.75 thousand pieces and, growing during the growing season of plants, it reaches 15.0 thousand pieces per 1 gram. abs. dry soil.

In the wheat + cotton variant, almost the same pattern is noted. In the variant wheat + solarization + cotton, the number of mushrooms does not exceed 2.0 pieces per 1 gram. abs. dry soil. Apparently, solarization had a detrimental effect on the development of fungi. In the variant wheat + solarization + mustard on

green manure + cotton, rapid development of fungi is noted in the period before cotton sowing and decreases by almost 50.0% in the period of cotton ripening.

This is due to the terms of decomposition of easily mobilizable organic material, which in our experience is the mustard Phyto mass.

The development of bacteria and actinomycetes also proceeded intensively in the variant where a large amount of organic material was plowed in, where bacteria amounted to 265.0 thousand pieces and actinomycetes 19.12 million pieces per 1 g. abs. dry soil. Among the bacteria, antagonistic forms predominated, which strongly inhibited the growth of the pathogen in pure culture.

Table 2 presents data on the isolation of various types of fungi into pure culture.

Tabular data show that with cotton monoculture, the total number of fungi is 7.75 thousand pieces in 1 g of abs. dry soil. Among isolated fungi were dominated by fungi such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium*. Isolation of *Trichoderma* is not observed. In the variant wheat + cotton with a total number of mushrooms in 1g abs. dry soil 7.75 thousand pieces *Aspergillus* was 3.0 thousand pieces, *Penicillium* 0.25 and *Fusarium* 0.75 thousand pieces in 1 year abs. dry soil.

In the variant wheat + cotton + solarization, the depressing effect of solarization is noted for all fungi, except for fungi of the genus *Aspergillus*.

In the variant wheat + solarization + mustard for green manure + cotton, before cotton sowing, there is a rapid development of fungi, especially from the genus *Aspergillus* 8.25 thousand pieces per 1 g abs. dry soil. Mushrooms from the genus *Penicillium* accounted for 1.75 thousand pieces in 1 g abs. dry soil. This variant had a detrimental effect on the development of fungi from the genus *Fusarium*. It was noted that the isolation of fungi from the genus *Trichoderma* in the amount of 0.25 thousand pieces per 1 g abs. dry soil.

During the period of cotton ripening, a decrease in the total number of fungi is observed, however, the number of fungi from the genus *Trichoderma* increases sharply and reaches 3.0 thousand pieces per 1 g of abs. dry soil (Fig.3).

Fig. 3. Natural strains of the fungus of the genus *Trichoderma* sp. dedicated from the option wheat + solarization + green manure.

As is known, among the fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* there are a lot of strains that are antagonists of soil pathogens, they may also have a detrimental effect on the development of fungi from the genus *Fusarium* simultaneously with solarization and sideration with mustard Phyto mass.

Table 2.

The total number of microorganisms in 1 g abs. dry soil.
Bukhara region, Vobkent district, farm "Kulkhatib", Variety Bukhara-10
April, August 2016

№	Experience options	Fungus, thous.		Bacteria, thous.		Actinomycetes, mln.	
		before sowing	in maturation	before sowing	in maturation	before sowing	in maturation
1.	Cotton by cotton	7,75	15,0	65,0	30,0	14,3	8,4
2.	Wheat + cotton	6,75	14,0	57,5	70,0	14,97	11,1
3.	Wheat + solarization + cotton	2,0	2,0	60,0	20,0	10,85	7,0
4.	Wheat + solarization + mustard (green manure) + cotton	13,25	7,0	265,0	260,0	19,12	9,6

Wilt development dynamics. Data on the dynamics of wilt development on cotton plants of the Bukhara-10 variety are presented in Table 3.

The table data show that in the cotton monoculture variant with 2-4 true leaves of plants, wilt-affected plants account for 35.0% (plant density 57.0 thousand units/ha). It should be noted that precise sowing was carried out at the rate of 90 thousand units/ha. Losses in the number of plants from wilt are almost 50.0%. During budding and maturation, the percentage of diseased plants is 8.0% and 15.0%, respectively. During

the ripening period of cotton (September 17), diseased plants accounted for 25.0% of external symptoms and 28.0% of wood tissue necrosis. Dried plants from the disease were not noted.

Almost similar results were obtained in the wheat + cotton variant during the cotton ripening period (the number of plants is 56.5 thousand pieces/ha), the percentage of plants with wilt is reduced by more than 50.0% (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Growth of cotton after wheat on field heavily infected with wilt.

Fig. 5. Cotton growth after wheat solarization + mustard for green manure under the fall.

In the variant wheat + solarization with the number of plants 85.5 thousand units/ha, diseased plants accounted for 3.5% - 4.0%. The best results were obtained in the variant wheat + solarization + mustard for green manure + cotton, at a plant density of 86.5 thousand pieces/ha, diseased plants ranged from 0.5% to 2.5% (Fig. 5).

Table 3

Dynamics of wilt development in cotton.
Bukhara region, Vobkent district, farm "Kulkhatib", Variety Bukhara - 10
2016

№	Experience Options	Quantity plants, thous./ha	Plants affected by wilt, %				
			2-4 present leaves	budding	Flowering-fruitful	maturation	
						on external prize	by necrosis
		10.07	30.05	10.07	14.08	17.09	17.09
1.	Cotton by cotton	57,0	35,0	8,0	15,0	25,0	28,0
2.	Wheat + cotton	56,5	28,0	6,8	7,9	9,5	11,0
3.	Wheat + solarization + cotton	85,5	4,0	2,5	2,0	3,5	4,0
4.	Wheat + solarization + mustard (green manure) + cotton	86,5	2,0	0,5	0,75	1,5	2,5

In the last two variants of the experiment from wilt, there is almost no loss in the number of plants per hectare. A slight decrease in plant density in these variants is possibly associated with other anthropogenic factors.

Biological harvest of raw cotton. Table 4 presents data on the biological yield of the Bukhara-10 variety. The data in Table 4 show that in the monoculture of cotton (control) at a plant density of 57.0 thousand pcs/ha, the yield of raw cotton is 28.0 q/ha.

Similar results were obtained when cultivating cotton after wheat in terms of plant density and yield.

When cultivating cotton after solarization at a plant density of 85.5 thousand pcs/ha, the biological yield was 47.4 centners/ha. The best results were obtained with the plowing of mustard phytomass under fallow grown after solarization, where the biological yield was 66.8 c/ha at a plant density of 86.5 thousand pcs/ha.

Table 4

Biological harvest of raw cotton
Bukhara region, Vobkent district, farm "Kulkhatib", Variety Bukhara-10
2016

№	Experience Options	Quantity plants, thous./ha	Raw cotton yield, c/ha	NSR ₀₅
1.	Cotton by cotton	57,0	28,0	1.3
2.	Wheat + cotton	56,5	28,8	0,1
3.	Wheat + solarization + cotton	85,5	47,4	1.4
4.	Wheat + solarization + mustard (green manure) + cotton	86,5	66,8	1.6

Conclusions

1. It has been established that during soil solarization, the wilt pathogen, the fungus *Fusarium* sp. is eradicated in the arable horizon, along with it, other soil microorganisms are also destroyed.

2. Sideration of the soil after solarization restores the natural microbiological potential of the soil and increases its antibiotic activity.

3. Soil manure after solarization reduces the incidence of wilt in the early stage of their development, preserves the number of plants and increases the yield of cotton.

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